

INTERCULTURALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION. IS SILENCE A REALIA ELEMENT?

Carolina DODU-SAVCA

PhD, Associate Professor

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4474-352X>

Marina Serbin (undergraduate student)

Free International University of Moldova

Tăcerea este semnificativă, autentică și obscură în egală măsură. În ciuda faptului că tăcerea poate fi resimțită ca un vid în comunicare, aceasta poate avea o importanță deosebită în diferite contexte culturale. Lipsa cuvântului este o formă de tăcere intenționată sau forțată; în ambele cazuri, tăcerea poate fi considerată o metodă eficientă de comunicare. Sensul tăcerii depinde de contextul general și cultural al unei interacțiuni. Potrivit concepției occidentale, tăcerea este adesea luată drept un semn de indiferență, apatie sau chiar atitudine ostilă. Deși în spațiul asiatic tăcerea are semnificație mai importantă, ea nu este percepută uniform. Similar acestei atitudini, în țările scandinave identificăm o tendință generală de a onora tăcerea, de a asculta mai mult decât de a purta o discuție și de a genera consens în conversație.

În cadrul interpretariatului și traducerilor, tăcerea poate fi atât intenționată, cât și circumstanțială. Acest fapt creează o imagine de ansamblu asupra motivelor de reușită sau eșec la nivelul sistemului sursă. Chiar și atunci când toate cuvintele sunt înțelese corect, tăcerea care le desparte poate fi receptată diferit. În acest sens, tăcerea este în continuare lăsată fără atenția cuvenită. Aceasta lipsă de interes este condiționată, oarecum, de faptul că tăcerea are un caracter bivalent și oferă numeroase posibilități de interpretare, inclusiv fiindcă este mai ușor să trecem sub tăcere ceea ce pare dificil de clarificat.

Cuvinte-cheie: *culturem, context cultural; interculturalitate; comunicare interculturală; comunicare între culturi; traducere intersemiotică.*

Abstract: *Silence is equally meaningful, authentic, and obscure. Although it can feel like a void in communication, silence can be powerful and expressive in different cultural contexts. The absence of speech is a form of intentional or enforced muteness that is considered a very effective method of communication.*

The meaning of silence depends on the situation and the cultural context of the interaction. In the Western world, silent behaviour is often perceived as a sign of indifference, apathy or hostility. Similar to Asian cultures, where silence is very respected, Scandinavian cultures tend to listen rather than talk and seek consensus in conversations. Silence in translation can be either intentional or accidental, which gives insight into the motives or failures of the source system. Although one understands all the words correctly, it is easy not to grasp the silence between them. Silence is still ignored. Perhaps because it has a bivalent character and offers much room for interpretation.

Keywords: *Realia; Cultural Context; Interculturality; Intercultural Communication, Cross-Cultural Communication; Intersemiotic Translation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In this article we propose a brief study that recognises that the characteristics of dependence and silence are appropriate in many cultures. Linguistic values have a direct influence on how we understand a foreign language and how it is rendered.

For many people, the main purpose of learning a foreign language is to communicate their thoughts and perceptions to people from other cultures. This paper shows that in order to communicate efficiently in an intercultural context, they need to depart from their habit of silence and vagueness. Generally, short answers followed by long pauses can seem awkward and make people in some cultures uncomfortable. In other words, if one wants to communicate one has to learn to translate by cushioning oneself (herself/himself) verbally to move from topic to topic without long silences. Excessively terse answers, vague responses and long silences are acceptable in a high-context culture, but in a low-context culture this kind of oblique interaction is neither pragmatic nor appreciated.

2. IS SILENCE A REALIA ELEMENT?

Although language, expression, and conversation are important topics in many studies, silence is usually passed over in silence. Ironically, it seems a simple matter to render silence and preserve the absence of sound. First, there is the paradox that silence is accentuated for speaking. Although it can feel like a void in communication, silence can have more than one meaning, depending on the cultural context. In the Republic of Moldova, if we consider the religious thinking, we should say that the

silence is seen as a gift from God. Silence appears, in this context, as a supreme means of communication. Only God can give you the gift to speak through silence. Just as we are silent in prayer, in sorrow or in joy. We are fortunate if our silence is noticed and understood by those around us, especially our loved ones.

According to Sedgwick [15], silence is more complex, it no longer merely conceals but also reveals, and language no longer merely reveals but also participates in concealment. In this way, silence and language rebel against semantically prescribed antonyms that would confine them to polar extremes, and instead develop an uncanny affinity for each other, a paradoxical affinity that actually attracts and even replaces them. This is exactly what Stanisław Jerzy Lec meant when he said “If you do not know his language, you will never understand a foreigner’s silence.”

Pamvo turned to others for a word of encouragement: “If my silence does not build him up, my word will not do him any good either”. From this perspective, the absence of speech as a form of deliberate muteness is presented as a very effective method of communication. The meaning of silence depends on the situation and the particular cultural context of the interaction. Another illustrative example of the division of the meaning of silence is Louis Massignon’s statement: “The silence of a man is a sign of refusal; the silence of a woman is a sign of agreement”.

According to Condon and Yousef [6], there are twenty-four aspects of non-verbal behaviour. One of these twenty-four aspects is silence. In this respect, it fulfils the same functions as non-verbal behaviour. In Western culture, silence is often seen as problematic, especially among native English speakers, Latin Americans and Italians. Silent behaviour is often perceived as a sign of indifference, apathy or hostility. As Samovar explains, most members of the dominant culture in the United States do not use silence extensively [14]. As Levinson found in his 2015 study [3], usually only a fraction of a second is allowed between two rounds of conversation. Like Levinson, Koudenburg believes that people feel uncomfortable when silence lasts longer than four seconds in a conversation [10].

In other cultures, silence is believed to be revered. Similar to Asians, Scandinavian cultures respect silence, listen rather than talk, and seek consensus in conversations. For this reason, the instinct of many Wester-

ners to fill every silence in a conversation can be perceived as intrusive and arrogant by their Asian counterparts.

Taking a cue from West Africa, they believe that “silence also speaks”. In other words, people are so familiar with each other that they do not need to fill every moment with talking. In Buddhism, silence is the only path to enlightenment, and Buddhist teachings can only be understood through silent contemplation and meditation. In the same approach, the outer realms deal with a person’s outer body and speech, while the inner realms are connected to silence, which they equate with truth [13].

The Asian mentality is based on this socio-psychological idea. The act of silence can also be used as an attempt to avoid something. The speaker hides his or her concerns or disagreement from the listener through polite and socially accepted silence, as opposed to the association between truthfulness and silence. [16] In harmony with family life, even if there is an apparent emotional distance between husband and wife, this relationship should be measured by whether the couple can understand each other without words. Couples prefer non-verbal communication to verbal communication when it comes to conveying their affection, because verbal communication is highly embarrassing [11]. In the words of the Chinese philosopher 老子 (Lǎozi), “Silence is a source of great power”. It is customary for Chinese to use silence as a sign of approval. Even if the listener knows the answer immediately, it is considered polite to give the listener some time to think about the answer. In Japan, a collectivist society with a strong group consciousness, silence is revered, which can be seen in the few words used to communicate.

Silences in this translation have to be identified as either deliberate or accidental, which also sheds light on either the motivations or the failures being vehiculated in the source system.

The silence in the translation may be either intentional or accidental, which gives insight into the motives or failure of the source system. The silence in the text, whether through omissions or intentionally created gaps, etc., together with various allusions - most likely understood by academics - ensured that a reader could decipher the message by reading between the lines, thus preserving intellectual freedom, especially through translations. According to Al-Quinai, the connotations of words are much more important than their denotations. Therefore, nothing is sensitive in itself, but the interpretation of its connotations makes it so. Thus,

silence, which is an integral part of the text as language in itself, plays the same role in the translated text as any other part of the source text by evoking associations that help the reader to read between the lines [2].

When silence is interpreted according to cultural norms and preconceived notions, cross-cultural communication fails because of this pragmatic mistranslation. When translators emphasise the function of silence, they do not neglect the communicative function of speech. Nevertheless, silence and speech fulfil complementary functions. A lack of knowledge about these functions can lead to misunderstandings and failure of translation.

Studying silence from an intercultural perspective helps to improve one's ability to translate between cultures. That is, silence in the context of semantic signs is a psycholinguistic behaviour. Translation requires enough time to organise an idea so that the translator can express the author's thoughts clearly and with enough information for the target language to understand.

In addition to cross-cultural communication, silence caused by affective signs can indicate lack of interest, hurt feelings or contempt. In line with high-context communication or messages, most of the information is already present in the person and very little information is contained in the coded, explicitly transmitted parts of the message. Low-context communication is presented as the opposite of this. According to Hall, Chinese culture is classified as a high-context culture, while American culture belongs to low-context cultures.[9]. In the light of Hall's classification, Samovar states that the meaning of information in high-context cultures is conveyed through gestures, the use of space and even silence [13]. In contrast, low-context cultures rely predominantly on verbal communication to convey information. In Chinese culture, however, the transmission of information is mainly determined by context. To decode a message, one must take into account the identity of the source text, the place, the time and the manner of speaking. Without this information, the message cannot be fully and accurately decoded. This hypothesis states that silence often conveys a stronger message than words and that someone who needs words does not have the necessary information.

In a study published in 2016, Reito Adachi examined how the American subtitles of Hayao Miyazaki's *Spirited Away* reflect silence. In a careful analysis, Adachi found that many of the silent moments in the

original version were replaced by sound effects, louder music and even dialogue [1].

In Elwood's study of Hayao Miyazaki's *Kiki's Delivery Service*, she also found that silent moments were replaced with dialogue added at moments when mouths were not visible or moving. In cases where silent moments are present in the source script and the translator feels that the original script lacks clarity, placeholders provide an opportunity for additional explanation [8]. As explained by Adachi, there are two types of dialogue: full and partial. In cases where a line of information is marked as fully added, a line of dialogue has been added to the original silence.

In partial substitution, certain information is retained, omitted and added. As for the Romanian translator's decision to keep the line from the English version instead of retaining the silence, we can assume that the translator either felt that the silence would be too long and unpleasant for the Romanian audience. In the translation into Romanian, much more dialogue was added than omitted. This result fits well with Adachi's findings on lost silences [1]. This is both because the Romanian version of the film is derived from the script of the English version.

Because of its ambiguity, cultural outsiders are likely to misunderstand the meaning of silence. It is therefore important to examine the causes of this misinterpretation, which are mainly due to the linguistic and cultural differences between nations. Understanding the cultural differences can facilitate effective cross-cultural communication. Silence itself can best be understood by looking at the contrasts without which it cannot be understood. In order to describe and express the manifestations of silence, and to be able to confront the fear or comfort that arises from its omnipresence, one should look beyond it and examine its different varieties and sources.

3. RENDERING AUDIOVISUAL – SILENCE ELEMENTS

XI Artwork, *Reverberations of Silence*, highlights a variety of ways to interpret silence and give it meaning. This collection looks at different aspects and interpretations of silence, such as: absence, absence and loss, fragmented, lost, hidden, obscured and erased texts, failures in communication, representations of recognisable empty categories and spaces in literary texts, as well as in cultural narratives, translations and language [16]. The main problem with translating the Chinese novel *Journey to the*

West into English is that it contains a large number of silent gaps, deliberate grammatical errors and unusual typography. According to Kristina Kočan, “the translator, who is first of all a reader”, has the special role of interpreting these absences and offering solutions in order to provide an adequate translation of the original text.

Katalin Balogné Bérces approaches the problem of silence in phonology from a partly theoretical point of view that seems to be valid for all languages, even if the examples are mainly for English. Silence is underpinned by voices, thoughts and emotions and is essential to the documentary narrative. Indeed, the curiosity of the target audience is directed towards all that is left unsaid. These moments of unspoken communication are full of truth about the characters’ opinions of each other and their reactions to what is happening around them. The relationship between sound, image and verbal content can be of:

- redundancy (one sign repeats or emphasizes another one);
- complementarity (the music announces a certain tension);
- autonomy (a zoom on an ashtray has nothing to do immediately with the current utterance);
- contradiction (a certain gesture can be opposed to what is said);
- distance (in order to be humorous or to create a sign of complicity);
- criticism (forcing the spectator to take a stand);
- help (the picture aids understanding of why things are said in a given way).

As to the verbal element in the AV (audiovisual) process, it can have different functions:

- explicative (offering, adding a piece of information, not shown in the pictures);
- performative (helping to do something);
- allocative (giving linguistic features in order to identify a character);
- demarcative (organizing the film narration, facilitating the progression of the plot);
- selective (directing the interpretation of a shot, a sequence).

Otherwise stated Zabalbeascoa believes that there are at least three main progressions: verbal, non-verbal and audiovisual [17]. As specified by Chaume, the meaning and scope of certain signs are always relative,

i.e. the importance of sound may predominate over visual semiotic forms in certain sequences; film code may predominate linguistic signs in other sequences. Film genres and types of AVT (audiovisual translation) can be classified according to this flexible analysis [5].

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMENDATION

As Théberge [4] claims, in the case of film “absolute silence cannot be allowed to occur [...] because it risks being interpreted, by audiences, as a technical breakdown”. Because it seems that silence cannot be grasped unless it is associated to something else. The final result of experiencing silence, should have a calming effect, but more common is pure horror.

Silence should not be automatically marked as the place where to offer a new dialogue, as recommended by all guidelines. Silence should be carefully considered, and its function and cultural symbolism should be understood.

The audio description strategy to audio portraits silence as a feature that has the same importance as any other narrative element and is undoubtedly part of the film language. While there is no golden rule on how silence should be audio described, in the present research was showed, through examples, different approaches to deal with rendering, and understanding silence. These endeavours have been classified as experiments, however, and have had no significant impact.

Narration is an element that is present in dubbing, it is considered to be another synonym for voice-over, although it can sometimes refer to a summary of the original dialogues, rather than a more or less literal translation. According to Díaz-Cintas [7], “AD (audio description) consists in transforming visual images into words, which are then spoken during the silent intervals of audiovisual programmes” [7].

However, as it is intralingual narration that consists of decodifying images and transforming them into words, what Roman Jakobson called intersemiotic translation, and many people do not consider it to be interlingual - proper translation. And yet the silence is still. Perhaps because it has a bivalent character and offers much room for interpretation. Or perhaps because it is easier to be silent about something that is more difficult to explain.”

References

1. ADACHI, Reito (2016) – *Dubbing of silences in Hayao Miyazaki's Spirited Away: A comparison of Japanese and English language versions*. *Perspectives*, 24:1, 142-156.
2. AL-QUINAI, Jamal (2005) – ‘Manipulation and Censorship in Translated Texts’ [Online]. Available: http://www.aieti.eu/pubs/actas/II/AIETI_2_JQ_Manipulation.pdf [Accessed 2021, May].
3. BÖGELS Sara, MAGYARI Lilia and LEVINSON Stephen C. (2015) – *Neural signatures of response planning occur midway through an incoming question in conversation*. *Scientific Reports*, 5, 1–11. Doi: 10.1038/srep12881.
4. BORDWELL, Théberge and THOMPSON, Kristin (2008) – *Film Art, An Introduction*. 8th edition. New York: McGraw Hill.
5. CHAUME, Frederic (2004) – ‘Film Studies and Translation Studies. Two disciplines at Stake in Audiovisual Translation’, *Meta* 49(1): 12–24.
6. CONDON, John C and YOUSEF, Fathi S. (1975) – *An Introduction to Intercultural Communication*, Macmillan Publishing Co.
7. DÍAZ CINTAS, Jorge (2008) – *Audiovisual Translation Comes of Age*, In *Between Text and Image: Updating Research in Screen Translation*, edited by D. Chiaro, C. Heiss, and C. Bucaria, 1–9. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
8. ELWOOD, Kate (2003) – *A Comparative Analysis of Requests in Majo no Takkyuubin and Kiki's Delivery Service*. Article. *Bunkaronshu*, 22, 213-236. An Interview with Cindy and Don Hewitt [Interview transcript]. (2021, December), Retrieved from Hayao Miyazaki Web site http://www.nausicaa.net/miyazaki/interviews/hewitt_interview.html
9. HALL, Edward T. and HALL, Mildred Reed (1990) – *Understanding Cultural Differences: Germans, French and Americans*, Yarmouth, ME: Intercultural Press.
10. KOUDENBURG, Namkje, POSTMES, Tom and GORDIJN, Ernestine H. (2011) – *Disrupting the flow: how brief silences in group conversations affect social needs*, *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*.
11. LEBRA, Takie (1984) – *Nonconfrontational Strategies for Management of Interpersonal Conflicts*, Eds. Krauss, Ellis S., Thomas

- P. Rohlen and Patricia G. Steinhoff, *Conflict in Japan*, Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1984b, p.43.
12. MAYNARD, Senko K. (1997) – *Japanese communication: language and thought in context*, Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, p.154.
 13. SAMOVAR, Larry A., *Communication Between Cultures*, Wadsworth Publishing Company, 1998.
 14. SEDGWICK, Eve Kosofsky: “A Poem Is Being Written,” 60; “Privilege of Unknowing,” 8n, 60n, 73, 0n; “Tide and Trust,” 60n.
 15. SIFIANOU, Maria. “Silence and politeness”. Ed. Jaworski, Adam. *Silence: interdisciplinary perspectives* Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter, 1997, p.66.
 16. SONTAG Susan, “The Aesthetics of Silence,” in *Styles of Radical Will*, (New York: Picador, 2002), 16.
 17. ZABALBEASCOA, P. (2008) ‘The Nature of the Audiovisual Text and its Parameters’, in J. Díaz Cintas (ed.) *The Didactics of Audiovisual Translation*, Amsterdam and Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 21–39.